

Understanding the Influence of Motivation on Requirements Engineering-related Activities

Dulaji Hidellaarachchi, John Grundy, Rashina Hoda, Ingo Mueller
*Department of Software Systems and Cybersecurity, Faculty of IT, Monash University
Melbourne, Australia*

1 Appendix A: Interview Protocol

Section 01: Demographic Information

- Can you briefly tell me about yourself?
- Considering your experience; how many years of experience do you have in the software industry?
- How many years of experience do you have in requirement engineering these years?
- Can you think of a past or a current software engineering project where you were engaged in RE-related activities?
 - Can you please tell me very briefly about that project?
 - Were you developing a product or service?
 - What software development methods are/were you using?
 - What are the size and composition of the team?
 - What is/was your role on the project?
 - What RE-related activities were being performed on that project?
 - What was your involvement in those activities?

Section 02: Views on the influence of motivation On RE-related activities

Motivation can be described as the willingness to do a certain action, for example, some people are motivated to work when they are given good feedback.

Talking about motivation;

- In your opinion, what are the aspects that motivate you when involved in RE-related activities?
- Can you explain how these aspects motivate you to perform RE-related activities? (Ask for more details about the factors they mentioned)
- Can you share your experience on how these motivation aspects impact on how you approach requirements engineering activities?

- Can you think of the most motivated team that you have ever been part of when involved in RE-related activities?
 - Can you tell me why you think it is a highly motivated team?
 - Did you feel highly motivated in that team? If so, what are the reasons for you to be highly motivated in that team?
- Now referring to the opposite of what you have mentioned, in your opinion, what are the aspects that demotivate you when involved in RE-related activities?
- Can you share your experience on how these demotivating factors impact on how you approach requirements engineering activities?
- Can you think of the most demotivated team (if any) that you have ever been part of when involved in RE-related activities?
 - Can you tell me why you think it is the demotivated team?
 - How did you handle the demotivating situation to get your work done?
 - Does your manager/ team leads/ senior management use any strategies to overcome demotivated situations?
 - If so, can you explain what are those?
 - Can you elaborate on how the demotivated situation impacted you to complete your tasks?
 - Did you attempt to stay motivated and make the project completed? If so, can you explain how?
- Any final thoughts about the impact of motivation on RE-related activities?

2 Appendix B: Detailed List of Collaborative & Human Motivation Factors and their influence on RE

Table 1: Influence of collaborative & human motivation factors on performing RE-related activities (Individual-related)

Sub-Category	Motivating/demotivating Factors	Impact on RE/SE	Responses
Individual	(+) Job satisfaction	Feeling of doing something useful leads to collect all the requirements needed Leads to happiness & satisfaction which motivates to do new activities Valuing the work done improves the quality of the solution Satisfied outcomes increase the involvement of other projects Less complains on requirements changes Complete the tasks successfully	21/21
	(+) Interacting with others	Improve collaborative thinking, helpful in providing advanced solutions Ability to identify missing/ incorrect requirements Enjoy direct conversations with customers to clarify unclear requirements Helpful in having in-depth discussions to elicit detailed requirements Interacting with the development team to come up with the technically most feasible approach for the client requirements	19/21
	(+) Individual interest	Highly involved in each tasks/activities from the beginning Helps to achieve goals & increase the quality of the service Makes the practitioners create novel/ highly practical features Dealing with challenging customers/situations to collect requirements	19/21
	(+) Personal satisfaction	Salary, incentives, promotions, recognition motivate individuals to achieve any goal The self-satisfaction of doing something useful will make practitioners perform well on given tasks Getting clarity of the role makes practitioners complete assigned tasks on time Wanting to do something big motivates them to dig deeper into requirements Positive appreciation may helpful in further development	19/21
	(+) Willingness to explore	Find efficient ways to gather requirements Learn & utilise new skills throughout the project Ability to react fast to the system/requirements changes due to keeping up with new technologies Provide advanced designs/ solutions to the problems Enhance individual performance result in quality outcome	18/21
	(+) Work-life balance	Ability to concentrate on the work properly Improve the quality of the work Less external impact on the tasks Improve personal satisfaction, result in on-time product delivery	17/21
	(+) Career development	Practitioners' involvement with clients to gain experience for career development, result in getting complete requirements Feeling of having personal development by working with the team, increases the engagement with the team, resulting in coming up with best solutions Getting experience for long-term career development makes the practitioners learn new skills & techniques and utilise them in RE	15/21
	(+) Hard-working nature	Doing work beyond expectations and completing tasks before the deadlines Keep on trying to improve, resulting in improving the quality of the work Getting detailed requirements from difficult to handle customers Committed to doing the work, resulting in successful project completion	15/21
	(+) Decision-making power	Easily conduct RE-related activities, specially elicitation with customers Ability to take the right decision on time, resulting in no project delays Decide whom to approach to have a direct talk/ long discussions on clients' side Helpful to be more responsible and giving 100% each task	12/21
	(+) Empathize with others	Helpful in understanding customers and their requirements Ability to design the system with less confusion Successfully play the intermediary role between the client and product development team until on-time product delivery	12/21
	(+) Problem-solving ability	Easily resolve complex requirements Finding the best/creative solution to the problems Understanding exact problem, resulting in getting clear requirements High quality final outcome result in customer satisfaction	09/21
	(+) Negotiation skills	Helpful in prioritizing requirements Important in dealing with customers on requirements changes Negotiations among team & customers on using different approaches to achieve specific goals	7/21
	(+/-) Language & communication	Good communication helps to obtain clear, detailed requirements Make the work efficient by direct, effective communication Obtain clear descriptions of what the system supposed to do which is essential for good performance Language barriers create difficulties on understanding the problem Taking more time to complete tasks due to poor communication	10/21
	(-) Personal issues	Personal issues related to families creates less involvement, resulting in incomplete tasks Insecure feelings at work create conflicts with others, resulting in quality of the work	7/21
(-) Irresponsible behaviour	Wasting time on completing tasks, result in exceeding the timeline & budget of the project Create conflicts between the team and the clients, resulting in getting incomplete requirements Completing tasks just to get by, impacting the quality of the final outcome of the project	6/21	

Table 2: Influence of collaborative & human motivation factors on performing RE-related activities (Team-related)

Sub-Category	Motivating/demotivating Factors	Impact on RE/SE	Responses
Team	(+) Cooperative team members	Support & opinions of the team easily solve the problems by making decisions and solutions together Cooperation among the team will increase the ability to work well by helping each other, result in final product in line with customer expectations Friendly collaboration will make the process fun and effective Collaboration with the team is helpful in knowledge sharing, doing RE clearly, making the product delivery on-time Helps to come up with better solutions with the collaboration of diverse people Helpful in understanding complex requirements	20/21
	(+) Knowledgeable team members	Understand complex requirements in particular domains Helpful in negotiating technical feasibility with customers Ability to solve problems easily Adding value to the project with their knowledge & skills, result in quality outcome Make it easy to deal with cross-functional teams in requirements gathering	19/21
	(+) Passionate team members	Provide high-quality outcome/solution Willing to learn new skills & keep updated with technology, benefited in achieving desired outcomes Focus on getting all the requirements clearly Always striving to do the best, result in delivering high-quality work	19/21
	(+) Committed team members	Involve in tasks and complete them beyond expectations Making the other team members motivated to do their work by giving their best Better understanding of requirements from the beginning and manage timelines accordingly Make the developers committed to delivering what customers exactly need	19/21
	(+) Responsible team members	Full-filling all the assigned tasks result in completing all the tasks in one story within a particular sprint Ability to backtrack any issues that occurred in the development of each story Not disregarding each and every task helpful in not missing any requirements Ensure the delivery of the project within the estimated time and budget Learn required skills and techniques to complete the assigned tasks (e.g., interviewing clients)	18/21
	(+) Equality of the team	Everyone's contribution in the team is helpful in understanding requirements easily Ability to approach to the people easily makes fewer conflicts on tasks Grow the responsibility and commitment towards the project with the sense of ownership resulting in high performance of the tasks Easy to work on dependencies of the functions increasing the progress of the project	17/21
	(+) Strong team bond	Helpful in solving complicated/ massive tasks with less time period Enhance the knowledge sharing among team members Creates positive environment among the team, resulting in a high team performance Helpful in having informal discussions to resolve problems and make the team learn from each others	17/21
	(+) Transparency of the team	Avoid potential risks of wrong interpretations of the requirements Get detailed information on changing requirements and their priorities Keeping everyone on the same page, reducing conflicts and incomplete tasks Enhance communication and coordination to complete tasks with trust	15/21
	(+) Understanding team	Ensure to assign tasks based on the expertise area, making early task completion Helpful in understanding technical difficulties and easy negotiations with customers Not being forced to work on tasks, resulting in quality outcome	7/21
	(+/-) Nature of the team	Energy of the team is helpful in completing tasks even before the estimated time Positive feelings (good vibes) of the team reduce insecurities within the team and show the progress of the project Enthusiasm of the team makes the whole development process fun and enjoyable Lazy team members avoid detailed discussions to gain clarity of requirements Unprofessional behaviours of the team make an unhappy environment, resulting in incomplete projects	13/21
	(+/-) Feedback	Helpful in improving user stories and prioritising product backlog Helpful in developing the project in the right direction, keeping customers satisfied Early preparation of the upcoming tasks in accordance with customer needs Getting wrong inputs/feedback (especially from customers) creates confusion of the product requirements	12/21
	(-) Team conflicts	Delays in product delivery as it takes more time than estimated to complete the assigned tasks Refusal to engage with others impact the final outcome Reduce the performance of the whole team and loose project interest Lead to missing requirements due to poor communication of conflicted team members	15/21
	(-) Poor team management	Takes more time to resolve problems with wrong estimations of the project Unable to complete high-priority tasks and create difficulties on the progress of the project Wasting the resources of the project without having any progress/ gain on the project	9/21

Table 3: Influence of collaborative & human motivation factors on performing RE-related activities (Customer/Clients/End user-related)

Sub-Category	Motivating/demotivating Factors	Impact on RE/SE	Responses
Customers Clients End users	(+) Knowledgeable customers	Knowing what they exactly need, helpful in getting clear & detailed requirements Having the right picture of the mind makes the designing of the project easier Helpful when working on massive complex projects Technical knowledge of the customers make the communication easier and more engagement with the development team	20/21
	(+) Cooperative customers	Provides meaningful responses to development team inquiries to understand complex requirements Reduce various project risks in later stages of the project Not getting last minute requirements changes Make the progress of the project smooth without conflicts or disturbances Clients' trust towards the project increases and helpful in negotiations related to technical feasibility	19/21
	(+) Customer satisfaction	Increase development team's interest and engagement towards the project Impacts on the organisation, its functions and reputation Increase development team's desire to complete all the required features	17/21
	(+) Customer availability	Helpful in clarifying unclear requirements or getting detailed requirements Development team gets a sense of understanding of what customers actually want Ability to complete tasks without any delays	16/21
	(+) Customer feedback	Acknowledging the work gives a sense of accomplishment to the team, resulting in the continuation of the hard work of the team Helpful in developing quality products in future projects Get the understanding of requirements related to their specific domain	14/21
	(-) Difficult to handle customers	Non-stop inquiries and issues from customers slow down the progress of the project Delays the progress of the project Additional pressure of dealing with customers take away practitioners' focus on the real problem and the requirements	11/21